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HR ANALYTICS AND THE GAME CHANGING TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The HR landscape is bound to change in the ensuing technology driven era. New technologies and innovative methods are being applied on HR data to assess the talent management practices of organizations and reinvent the importance of HR functions. Some of the researchers made early predictions as “any discussion on the Future of HR needs to include a focus on developing analytical skills” (Nolan Sara, 2012), which are turning out to be true. Analytics has been described as a ‘must have’ capability for the Human Resource (HR) profession, a tool for creating value from people and a pathway to broadening the strategic influence of the HR function (CIPD, 2013). Organizations are increasingly investing in technology and data sources than in the past. PwC in its 2014 HR Technology Survey, reported that 56% of the respondent organizations had a formal HR Technology strategy, whereas another 25% have plans to move their HR analytic technology to the cloud over the next one-to-three years. Leading business organizations have already started applying their analytical capabilities on HR functions, whereas other firms are yet to catchup. Advent of Big data and other open source environments like ‘R’ have created much space for analytics to grow and flourish. On the other hand, tech-giants are developing several products to meet the analytics needs of the business organizations. In this backdrop, the current paper discusses HR analytics function from the technology point of view. The paper reviews and presents some of the key technologies that are driving HR analytics.

Key words: HR Analytics, Big Data, R, HR Technologies

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INTRODUCTION

People Analytics or HR Analytics is not an entirely new concept. Prevalence of data analytics in general and HR analytics in particular is existent in organizations in different forms since very long. The field of HR analytics is a result of challenging the routine. Though some of the organizations have been adopting certain metrics and tools such as Human Resource Accounting and Score Cards, they were inadequate to give a strategic advantage to the firms in terms of their human capital. The performance and results of Human resources and their activities was going unmeasured. According to Caudron (2004), Jac Fitz-enz was the first to propose a radical, anti-establishment idea of measuring human resources activities and assessing their impact on the bottom line as early as in 1978. However, this idea was not well received and followed at that time as there were neither proper metrics nor the technology to measure the same was developed. Jac Fitz-enz continued his campaign and developed his ideas further on measuring human resource activities. Research expanded to develop relevant HR metrics. Organizations did not realize the potential of measuring HR outcomes until recent times. By the 1990s organizations started focusing on benchmarking HR metrics.

The advent of software and automation technology by 2000s and their application to Human Resource (HR) field generated abundant data which can be further processed and analyzed. This simplified the requirement of tedious procedures to understand HR dimensions.

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profession, a tool for creating value from people and a pathway to broadening the strategic influence of the HR function (CIPD, 2013). Organizations are increasingly investing in technology and data sources than in the past. PwC in its 2014 HR Technology Survey, reported that 56% of the respondent organizations had a formal HR Technology strategy, whereas another 25% have plans to move their HR analytic technology to the cloud over the next one-to-three years.

To transform from analog to digital, HR organizations must integrate new technology that will allow them to reinvent themselves and get out in front of the dramatic changes in the highly competitive market for recruiting, retaining and developing employees (Goldstein, 2015). All things put together a separate booming field of data analytics has come to the business as ‘business analytics’. The application of the capabilities of business analytics to the particular data needs of human resource function and the corresponding people related decisions is labelled as ‘workforce analytics’ or ‘people analytics’.

TECHNOLOGICAL CAPABILITIES BOOSTING THE POWER OF HR ANALYTICS

Technology has enabled all business functions and processes. Use of electronic forms of data and execution of business functions through electronic forms has become key for the success of business. Along with all other business functions, the Human Resources (HR) function is also being managed more electronically.

The advent of technology has created surge in the data capturing and storage capabilities of HR functions. Parallel to the other information systems and functions in organizations, HR

information systems have also transformed to integrate the HR data with various business functions.

This upsurge enabled HR managers to utilize the data in all possible means to develop better HR metrics for the organization. Development of new HR metrics has become essential as organizations are looking to gauge the performance of all functional areas in realistic terms; for this, supportive metrics are the only means of evidence.

TECHNOLOGY SURGE: FROM INFORMATION SYSTEMS TO ANALYTICS

The popularity of Information systems grew with the introduction of computer technology into organizations. Basic forms of Management Information Systems (MIS) and Decision Support Systems (DSS) have been the tools that business decisions were relied upon. Executive Information Systems (ESS) provided the necessary data support for top level managements. In all these forms of information systems data existed in different forms, types and many places. A data integration and handling approach surfaced with the emergence of ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) packages. ERP packages helped in improving the routine and semi structured decision making. Some of the ERP packages began offering business intelligence as one of the modules of the ERP package. Business intelligence played key role with more organizations embracing the ERP technologies for increased business agility. However, with the advancement of software and corresponding data technologies such as data warehousing, data mining, and OLAP (Online Analytical Processing), business intelligence came into limelight and occupied predominant place until recent times.

Business Intelligence: Business intelligence uses data and statistical methods and develops metrics to measure the past performance of business and lead the direction for business decisions. According to Hoboken, N.J. “Business intelligence (BI) is a set of theories, methodologies, processes, architectures, and technologies that transform raw data into meaningful and useful information for business purposes.” Business intelligence uses tools such as online analytical processing (OLAP) to report, query, and summarize the frequency, quantity, location and trends of the business actions and the counter actions that need to be taken. One of the key limitation of business intelligence tools is their high reliance on pre-determined metrics and feeble interaction with business actions and outcomes. This led to the development of business analytics as a separate field.

Table 1: Summary of Phases of Business Analytics, Methods, Technologies, and Tools Used

PHASE OF BUSINESS ANALYTICS				
	BASIC REPORTING	DESCRIPTIVE / INFERENTIAL ANALYTICS	PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS	PRESCRIPTIVE ANALYTICS
METRICS / METHODS USED	Rate, Ratio, Composition, Index, Volume, Cost, Time, Quality, Satisfaction	Frequency distributions, Cumulative distributions, Measures of central tendency, Measures of	Regression: Linear, Non-linear, Factor Analysis, Cluster Analysis, Statistical modeling,	Simulation, Optimization, use of mathematical and computational models combined with business rules that are

PHASE OF BUSINESS ANALYTICS				
SCOPE OF APPLICATION / PRESENTATION	BASIC REPORTING	DESCRIPTIVE / INFERENTIAL ANALYTICS	PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS	PRESCRIPTIVE ANALYTICS
		dispersion, Correlation, Hypothesis testing	Machine learning, Data Mining	actionable and providing feedback
		Presentation of past data in summarized forms	Presentation of highly summarized data with indicative trends and relations	Presentation of predicted/future data based on highly summarized past data, Sentiment analysis
		Presentation of future outcomes along with decision implications on business		
TYPE OF REPORTS	Standard Reports	Ad Hoc reports, Queries, Drill down,	Alerts, Statistical Analysis, Predictive models	Optimization, Stochastic optimization,
SOFTWARE / TOOLS	Dashboards, Microsoft	Microsoft Excel based analysis,	Statistical Software like	Statistical Software like

PHASE OF BUSINESS ANALYTICS				
	BASIC REPORTING	DESCRIPTIVE / INFERENTIAL ANALYTICS	PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS	PRESCRIPTIVE ANALYTICS
	Excel based tabulations, Business Intelligence reporting tools, ERP reporting tools	Business Intelligence reporting tools, Statistical Software like SPSS, SAS, R etc.	SPSS, SAS, R etc.	SPSS, SAS, R etc. along with the integrated tools to Model business scenarios

SHIFT IN USAGE OF TECHNOLOGIES

Leading companies are using sophisticated data collection technology and analysis to get the most value from their talent. These companies have taken the guesswork out of employee management by leveraging analytics to improve their methods of attracting and retaining talent, connecting their employee data to business performance, differentiating themselves from competitors, and more. Human Resources Analytics provides organizations detailed analysis on HR programs and workforce performance. It integrates critical data from across the enterprise value chain transforming silos of information into relevant, timely, and actionable insight. Human resources analytics, also called talent analytics, is the application of sophisticated data mining and business analytics (BA) techniques to human resources (HR) data. To define, HR analytics is an evidence-based approach for making better decisions on the people side of the business; it consists of an

array of tools and technologies, ranging from simple reporting of HR metrics all the way up to predictive modeling.

Whereas descriptive analytics reveals current data patterns, predictive analytics gives meaning to those patterns for the future. With practice, one can look at historical data and foretell, to some degree, the likelihood of a future occurrence. The Predictive analytics expresses the future in terms of probabilities. It helps management make decisions that minimize risks and increase ROIs. No analytic application can predict the future with absolute certainty; but, when properly applied it will substantially reduce variability. Models are an example of a predictive application.

Predictive management, or HCM:21 (human capital management for the twenty-first century): This breakthrough program was developed over a period of eighteen months as part of Predictive Initiative, a consortium of major organizations and thought leaders who were committed to transforming people management into a strategic function. HCM:21, or human capital management, is the framework of logic that is used to gather, organize, and interpret data, and subsequently also knowledge, for assessing the probability of upcoming events. HCM takes the gambling out of decision making. It helps overcome a reliance on past data and obsolete experience, and replace it with insights regarding the future and the tools for influencing it. HCM:21 is a four-phase process that starts with scanning the market-place and ends with an integrated measurement system. In the middle, it addresses workforce and succession planning in a new way and shows how to optimize and synchronize the delivery of HR services (Fitz-Enz, J, 2010).

CONCLUSION

There is a vast scope for improving both individual and organizational performance through HR analytics. It becomes possible because through analytics one can identify the various areas where money, time and efforts can be better utilized. . Business analytics is being focused more than any other technology in the past decade. The popularization of bigdata and the subsequent development of analytical tools has greatly influenced the growth of business analytics. With more organizations adapting business analytics, organizations are obsessed to spread the application of analytics into all domains. Use of analytics in the field of HR has also gained momentum. Digitalization of HR dashboards has helped in producing updated insights about the organizations workforce status. HR analytics will also be helpful in assessing the strategic impact of HR on business and other core HR functions. Areas of talent planning, acquisition, retention, training, performance management and succession planning can be improved significantly by using the results of the organization's HR analytics. A review of various studies and the corresponding literature available about people analytics proves that there is a greater scope to position people analytics to use as a strategic enabler i.e., the one to play crucial role in defining the strategic decisions of the firm that have a bearing on the long-term performance of the company. The future of people analytics as an important function in organization is vast.

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